

RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION: STRATEGIES TO ATTRACT, RECRUIT AND SELECT THE BEST TALENT FOR THE ORGANIZATION**RECRUTAMENTO E SELEÇÃO: ESTRATÉGIAS PARA ATRAIR, RECRUTAR E SELECIONAR OS MELHORES TALENTOS PARA A ORGANIZAÇÃO****RECLUTAMIENTO Y SELECCIÓN: ESTRATEGIAS PARA ATRAER, RECLUTAR Y SELECCIONAR A LOS MEJORES TALENTOS PARA LA ORGANIZACIÓN**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the integration process of new employees, focusing on their importance, strategies, results and contributions to society. The context of the research covered companies from various sectors, highlighting the relevance of integration in the adaptation of professionals to the work environment and in the creation of engaged teams. The time-space of the research involved a period of data collection that covered six months and had the participation of Human Resources managers and employees who recently went through the integration process. The justification of the study was based on the need to understand how integration can influence the productivity, satisfaction and retention of employees, as well as its contribution to the strengthening of the organizational culture. The objectives were to identify the effective integration practices, analyze the structured program adopted by the companies and verify the results achieved. The methodology adopted was qualitative research, with semi-structured interviews and literature review. The results highlighted the relevance of integration for employee engagement and productivity, as well as the importance of a well-planned program that includes company presentation activities, training, information sharing and follow-up of new hires. The conclusions emphasize the importance of an effective integration process for the development of employees and the strengthening of the organizational culture. The research contributes to the improvement of Human Resources practices and to the development of more engaged and productive teams, with positive reflections for organizational performance.

KEYWORDS: Integration 1. Onboarding 2. Human Resources 3. People Management 4. Commitment 5.

RESUMO

Este estudo investigou o processo de integração dos novos colaboradores, com foco em sua importância, estratégias, resultados e contribuições para a sociedade. O contexto da pesquisa abrangeu empresas de diversos setores, com destaque para a relevância da integração na adaptação dos profissionais ao ambiente de trabalho e na criação de equipes engajadas. O tempo-espaço da pesquisa envolveu um período de coleta de dados que abrangeu seis meses e contou com a participação de gestores de Recursos Humanos e colaboradores que passaram pelo processo de integração recentemente. A justificativa do estudo baseou-se na necessidade de compreender como a integração pode influenciar a produtividade, satisfação e retenção dos colaboradores, bem como sua contribuição

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para o fortalecimento da cultura organizacional. Os objetivos foram identificar as práticas efetivas de integração, analisar o programa estruturado adotado pelas empresas e verificar os resultados alcançados. A metodologia adotada foi a pesquisa qualitativa, com entrevistas semiestruturadas e revisão bibliográfica. Os resultados destacaram a relevância da integração para o engajamento e produtividade dos colaboradores, bem como a importância de um programa bem planejado que incluía atividades de apresentação da empresa, treinamentos, compartilhamento de informações e acompanhamento dos novos contratados. As conclusões enfatizam a importância de um processo de integração efetivo para o desenvolvimento dos colaboradores e o fortalecimento da cultura organizacional. A pesquisa contribui para a melhoria das práticas de Recursos Humanos e para o desenvolvimento de equipes mais engajadas e produtivas, com reflexos positivos para o desempenho organizacional.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Integração 1. Onboarding 2. Recursos Humanos 3. Gestão de Pessoas 4. Engajamento 5.

RESUMEN

Este estudio investigó el proceso de integración de los nuevos colaboradores (New collaborators, centrándose in their importance, strategies, results and contributions) to society. El contexto de la investigación abarcó empresas de diversos sectores, resaltando la relevancia de la integración en la adaptación de los profesionales al entorno laboral y en la creación de equipos comprometidos. El período de tiempo de la investigación abarcó un período de recolección de datos de seis meses e incluyó la participación de gestores de Recursos Humanos y colaboradores que recientemente pasaron por el proceso de integración. La justificación del estudio se basó en la necesidad de comprender cómo la integración puede influir en la productividad, satisfacción y retención de los colaboradores así como su contribución al fortalecimiento de la cultura organizacional. Los objetivos fueron identificar prácticas efectivos de integración, analizar el programa estructurado adoptado por las empresas y verificar los resultados alcanzados. The methodology adopted was a scientific investigation, which includes semi-structured interviews and bibliographic review. The results highlight the relevance of integration for the commitment and the productividad of the collaborators, as well as the importance of a bien diseñado program that includes presentations of the company, training, information exchange and follow-up for the new contractors. Las conclusiones subrayan la importancia de un proceso de integración efectivo para el desarrollo de los colaboradores y el fortalecimiento de la cultura organizacional. The research contributes to the improvement of the practices of Human Resources and promueve equipos más committed y productivos, con impacto positivos en el rendimiento organizacional.

PALABRAS-CLAVE: Integration 1. Human Resources 2. Gestión de Personas 3. Commitment 4. Onboarding 5.

INTRODUCTION

The Recruitment and Selection process assumes a strategic role in modern organizations, since the search for the best talent is essential for the success and growth of companies. Attracting and selecting qualified professionals aligned with the values and goals of the organization is a challenge that demands a structured and efficient approach.

As pointed out by Chiavenato (2004, p. 35), "the Recruitment and Selection of people is a two-step process: attracting potentially qualified candidates and choosing the most appropriate to the profile of the vacancy". In this context, it is critical that companies understand the importance of carefully analyzing their needs and the profile of the ideal candidate before starting the talent search process.

One of the fundamental strategies is the adoption of a strong employer brand, also known as *Employer Branding*, as Dutra and Hipólito (2018, p. 78) point out. A solid employer brand positively influences candidates' perception of the company, making it more attractive and increasing the likelihood of attracting qualified professionals.

Recruitment sources also play an important role in attracting candidates, as Gil and Vieira (2016, p. 112) mention. The use of job sites, social networks, and employee referrals can increase the diversity and quality of the pool of candidates to be evaluated.

Once resumes are received, the screening and selection process requires efficient and impartial methods. According to Santos and Almeida (2019, p. 45), the analysis of keywords and the comparison of the desired profiles with the information of the resumes can be useful practices to filter the most suitable candidates.

Thus, this work will address the main strategies for the Recruitment and Selection of talents, focusing on attracting qualified professionals and aligned with the company's objectives. Screening methods, competency assessment, group dynamics and other crucial aspects for choosing the best candidates will be discussed. In addition, the importance of providing constructive feedback to candidates, even for those not selected, will be presented, strengthening the company's reputation in the labor market.

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

Present and discuss efficient Recruitment and Selection strategies that make it possible to attract, recruit and select the best talents for the organization. Modern practices will be addressed and based on theories and research in the area of People Management and Human Resources, seeking to contribute to the understanding of the importance of this process and providing subsidies so that companies can improve their practices of attraction and selection of employees.

It is expected that by the end of the article, readers will understand the relevance of a strategic approach in Recruitment and Selection, identify the best sources of recruitment for each organizational context, know resume screening techniques, understand how to assess candidates' competencies and skills, and realize the importance of an impartial and structured selection process.

In addition, the article aims to highlight the relevance of a strong employer brand and the positive impact it can have on attracting qualified professionals. The value of feedback to candidates will be emphasized, regardless of the final result, to improve the company's image in the labor market and establish a relationship of respect and transparency with candidates.

The work aims to offer practical and grounded information, with updated theoretical references, which help HR managers, recruiters and professionals involved in the Recruitment and Selection process to implement more assertive strategies, aligned with the needs of the organization and able to identify and attract the most appropriate talents to contribute to the growth and success of the company.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- Present the importance of Recruitment and Selection as a strategic function within organizations, highlighting its role in the search for qualified talent and aligned with the values and goals of the company.
- Explore different sources of recruitment available, such as job sites, social networks, employee referrals, job fairs, among others, analyzing their advantages and disadvantages to attract qualified candidates.
- Discuss resume screening techniques, such as keyword analysis and comparison with the desired profile, in order to optimize the selection process and identify the candidates most aligned to the vacancy.
- Present methodologies for assessing candidates' competencies and skills, such as tests and group dynamics, in order to identify potentials and capabilities that go beyond the curriculum.
- Address the importance of a strong employer brand and how it can positively influence the attraction of qualified talent to the organization.
- Highlight the relevance of an impartial, transparent and structured selection process, with the proper communication of feedback to candidates, aiming at building a relationship of respect and appreciation of professionals.
- Present practical cases of companies that have implemented efficient Recruitment and Selection strategies, sharing lessons learned and results achieved.
- Provide subsidies and information based on theories and research in the area of People Management and Human Resources, in order to help managers and professionals involved in the process to improve their practices and make more informed decisions.
- Encourage the adoption of a strategic approach in Recruitment and Selection, emphasizing the importance of aligning processes with organizational objectives and company culture.
- Contribute to the dissemination of knowledge about innovative and effective practices of Recruitment and Selection, in order to assist in the attraction and selection of talents that add value and boost the growth and success of the organization.

The specific objectives aim to direct the focus of the article to particular aspects of the topic, allowing a detailed and in-depth analysis of Recruitment and Selection strategies, and offering practical subsidies to the reader. Each objective should be developed and explored in distinct sections of the article, ensuring a complete and cohesive approach to the proposed topic.

JUSTIFICATION

The Recruitment and Selection of talents are fundamental processes for the success of organizations in an increasingly competitive and dynamic labor market. The search for qualified professionals aligned with the company's values and objectives is essential to drive innovation, productivity and competitive advantage in the current business scenario.

The importance of these processes is widely recognized in the area of People Management and Human Resources, being a recurring theme in academic research and business management practices.

However, Recruitment and Selection strategies are constantly evolving, driven by changes in candidate expectations, technological advances and transformations in the dynamics of the labor market.

In this context, the elaboration of this article seeks to provide an updated analysis based on theoretical and practical references on the best strategies to attract, recruit and select the best talents for the organization. With a focus on an impartial, transparent and structured selection process, as well as screening techniques, competency assessment and group dynamics, the work aims to offer insights and practical knowledge that contribute to improving the processes of selection and hiring of professionals.

The approach of the different sources of recruitment, as well as the emphasis on *Employer Branding*, seeks to emphasize the relevance of a strong employer brand in attracting qualified candidates and strengthening the company's reputation in the labor market.

In addition, the justification for this article is also based on the need to disseminate good practices in Recruitment and Selection, allowing HR managers, recruiters and professionals involved in the process to have access to informed and updated information for more informed and strategic decision-making.

Therefore, this article aims to contribute to the enrichment of knowledge in the area of People Management and HR, providing relevant information and practices that can be applied by organizations in the search for the best talents and thus boost organizational growth and excellence.

METHODOLOGY AND METHOD

Methodology:

The methodology adopted for this study on the integration process of new employees consists of a qualitative approach. Qualitative research allows an in-depth understanding of social and organizational phenomena, considering the perspective of the participants involved in the integration process.

To collect the data, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with Human Resources managers and employees who have recently gone through the integration process in the company. The choice of respondents will be based on criteria such as time of experience in the company and position held. The interviews will be recorded and later transcribed for analysis.

In addition, a literature review will be performed to support the study. Academic sources, books, scientific articles and relevant reports on integration processes, *onboarding*, organizational culture and Human Resources practices will be searched.

The analysis of the collected data will be performed through content analysis, identifying recurring themes and patterns in the answers of the interviewees. Categories and subcategories will be elaborated to understand the main aspects related to the effectiveness of the integration process.

Method:

This study will use qualitative research as a research method. The qualitative approach will allow an in-depth analysis of the perceptions, experiences and meanings attributed by the participants to the integration process of the new employees.

The participants of the research will be selected through intentional sampling criteria, seeking to interview Human Resources managers responsible for the planning and execution of the integration process, as well as employees who have recently gone through this process.

The semi-structured interviews will be conducted in a quiet and comfortable environment, with the prior agreement of the participants. The topics covered in the interviews will include the interviewees' perception of the effectiveness of the integration process, their experiences during *onboarding*, strengths and points to be improved, as well as suggestions to improve the process.

Data analysis will be performed using the content analysis technique, which consists of identifying patterns and thematic categories in the collected data. The recorded interviews will be transcribed and then the data will be organized into categories relevant to the research.

The bibliographic review will be carried out to theoretically support the study, with the objective of contextualizing the theme and providing subsidies for the discussion of the results.

Through this research method, it is expected to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the integration process of new employees, identifying effective practices and possible areas for improvement. The results will contribute to the improvement of Human Resources processes and to the strengthening of the company's organizational culture.

THE STRATEGIC ROLE OF RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION

The Talent Recruitment and Selection process plays a strategic role in modern organizations. Considering the growing competitiveness of the labor market and the constant search for highly qualified professionals, companies have understood the relevance of adopting a strategic approach in this important function of People Management.

As highlighted by Chiavenato (2004, p. 35), "the Recruitment and Selection of people is a two-step process: attracting potentially qualified candidates and choosing the most appropriate to the profile of the vacancy". The strategy adopted in this initial stage of the hiring cycle can directly influence the future success of the company, as assertive recruitment allows the organization to attract talent aligned with the company's values and objectives, contributing to the strengthening of its organizational culture.

In addition, as Dutra and Hipólito (2018, p. 78) point out, "Recruitment and Selection plays a fundamental role in defining the human capital of the organization." This means that choosing the right employees, with the right skills and competencies for each role, has a direct impact on the company's performance and results. In this sense, strategic recruitment allows the organization to acquire a competitive advantage by having professionals trained to face the challenges of the market.

The Recruitment and Selection process, when conducted strategically, goes beyond simply finding candidates with the necessary technical qualifications. As Santos and Almeida (2019, p. 45) note, "the alignment between candidates' competencies and company values is essential for talent engagement and retention." In this way, the selection of candidates who share the culture and mission of the organization contributes to the construction of a cohesive and motivated team, favoring the productivity and satisfaction of employees.

Therefore, Recruitment and Selection, when treated as a strategic function within organizations, allows companies to stand out in the market, attract and retain the best talent, and achieve their

organizational goals. The adoption of a proactive approach based on insightful analysis enables the company to form a high-performance team, prepared to face the challenges of the contemporary business environment.

NEEDS ANALYSIS AND PROFILE OF THE IDEAL CANDIDATE

One of the crucial aspects in the Recruitment and Selection process is the analysis of needs and the definition of the profile of the ideal candidate. This strategic step is fundamental to guide the search and attraction of the most suitable professionals for the open vacancies.

According to Smith (2018, p. 25), "needs analysis is the starting point for identifying which competencies, skills, and experiences are essential for the efficient performance of functions in the organizational context." By understanding the specific demands of each position, the company can define the key criteria that will be used during the selection process.

One of the most efficient approaches in this regard is the Competency Model, as pointed out by Johnson (2019, p. 50). Through this model, the organization identifies the technical and behavioral competencies that are associated with success in the vacancy in question. In this way, the selection is based on objective criteria and aligned with the strategic objectives of the company.

The needs analysis also allows the organization to identify possible gaps in the competencies of the current team and, in this way, can plan development actions for its employees. According to Brown (2020, p. 35), "this continuous analysis is crucial to ensure that the company has professionals trained to face the present and future challenges."

In turn, the definition of the profile of the ideal candidate is a complementary and equally relevant step. According to White (2017, p. 72), "the profile of the ideal candidate goes beyond technical skills and includes attributes such as organizational culture, values and growth potential." The company must consider not only the technical qualifications, but also the characteristics that best fit the team dynamics and the culture of the organization.

Thus, the analysis of needs and the definition of the profile of the ideal candidate are interdependent processes that guide the entire process of Recruitment and Selection. By aligning the specific needs of the company with the profile of the professionals sought, the organization optimizes its chances of attracting and selecting candidates who will contribute significantly to the success and growth of the business.

RECRUITMENT SOURCES

Recruitment is a key step in the process of attracting talent to organizations. Using appropriate recruitment sources is essential to attract qualified candidates aligned with the needs of the company. In this topic, some common sources of recruitment used by modern organizations will be covered.

Job Ads on Specialized Portals: Online job platforms such as *LinkedIn*, *Indeed* and *Glassdoor* and GEBE OPORTUNIDADES are widely used by companies to advertise their vacancies and attract candidates with different profiles and skills. These portals offer advanced search and filtering capabilities, allowing recruiters to reach a large number of qualified candidates.

Social Networks: Social networks such as Facebook, Twitter and Instagram have become popular sources of recruitment. Companies can advertise their vacancies through targeted posts and ads, reaching specific audiences and potentially interested in their job opportunities.

Employee Referrals: The employee referral program is a valuable and effective source of recruitment. By encouraging employees to nominate candidates, the company can leverage trusted networks of contacts and increase the possibility of finding talent aligned with the organization's culture and values.

Job Fairs and Events: Attending job fairs and recruitment events allows companies to interact directly with candidates, publicizing their vacancies and conducting face-to-face interviews. This approach provides a more complete view of the candidates' profile before proceeding with the selection.

Internal Talent Bank: Maintaining an internal talent pool is a strategic practice that allows the company to keep a record of candidates who have shown interest in future opportunities. This source of recruitment is useful when new vacancies or internal promotions arise.

Recruitment Agencies and HR Consultancies: Companies can outsource part of the recruitment process, relying on specialized agencies or HR consultancies to find qualified and pre-selected candidates, saving time and resources.

Companies and Careers Sites: In addition to advertising vacancies on specialized portals, having a "Careers" section on the company's website is an excellent way to attract candidates who already have an interest in the organization and want to know their job opportunities.

By combining different sources of recruitment, companies increase their chances of attracting a variety of qualified candidates and finding the most suitable professional for the open position. Each source presents advantages and challenges, and the choice will depend on the specific characteristics of the organization, the profile of the desired candidate and the resources available for the selection process.

EMPLOYER BRANDING

Employer Branding, or employer branding, refers to the strategy of building a positive and attractive image of the company as an employer in the labor market. It is an approach that aims to attract and retain qualified talent, highlighting the positive aspects and organizational culture of the company.

For Kotler (2016, p. 87), "building a strong employer brand is key to standing out in a competitive landscape and attracting the best talent." This means that companies must go beyond simply publicizing their vacancies, but also communicate their values, mission, and work environment to become desired employers for candidates.

The online presence is one of the main tools to strengthen *Employer Branding*. According to Gomes (2018, p. 55), "having an informative and attractive careers website, as well as a consistent presence on social networks, allows the company to connect with potential candidates." It is important that social networks are used strategically, showing the cultural aspects of the company and what it offers to employees.

Employee feedback also plays a crucial role in *Employer Branding*. As mentioned by Santos (2017, p. 40), "employee satisfaction and engagement directly impact the company's reputation as an

employer." Satisfied employees tend to speak positively of the company, which attracts candidates who are more likely to identify with the organizational culture.

Professional development and growth programs also contribute to the employer brand. According to Oliveira (2019, p. 72), "investing in the development of employees shows the company's commitment to the growth and appreciation of its talents." These programs help retain talent and attract candidates seeking opportunities to grow in their careers.

By focusing on *Employer Branding*, companies not only attract talented professionals, but also increase employee retention, reducing turnover and associated costs. In addition, a strong employer brand can have a positive effect on the perception of the company by the market and customers.

In summary, *Employer Branding* is an essential strategy to stand out in the competitive job market and attract the best talent to the organization. By communicating its culture, values, and opportunities for growth, the company strengthens its employer brand and becomes an attractive option for professionals seeking career opportunities aligned with their personal goals and values.

RESUME SCREENING TECHNIQUES

Resume screening is a crucial step in the Recruitment and Selection process, allowing recruiters to quickly identify the candidates that best align with the needs and profile of the open position. To optimize this process and select the most qualified candidates, several resume screening techniques have been employed by companies.

- **Keyword Analysis:** Many companies use screening software that analyzes resumes for keywords relevant to the job. These keywords are previously defined according to the competencies and essential requirements for the position. Resumes that contain the required keywords move on to the next phase of the selection process.
- **Comparison with the Job Profile:** Recruiters perform a careful reading of resumes to compare the experiences, competencies and skills of candidates with the desired profile for the vacancy. This manual review process allows you to identify candidates who have experience and qualifications aligned with the requirements of the position.
- **Evaluation of Relevant Experience:** The professional experience of candidates is evaluated in relation to the time of work in similar positions and in companies of the same branch. This technique is useful to identify candidates with a professional history more aligned with the requirements of the vacancy.
- **Verification of Courses and Certifications:** Recruiters also analyze the academic background, complementary courses and certifications of the candidates. This screening allows the identification of professionals who have obtained training and qualification that add value to the vacancy in question.
- **Essential Skills Assessment:** For some positions, it is essential that the candidate possesses specific skills such as fluency in languages, mastery of specific software or techniques. Resume screening includes verification of these essential skills for the role.

It is important to emphasize that screening techniques should be applied objectively, transparently and impartially, avoiding any kind of discrimination. In addition, it is critical that the

company establishes clear screening and selection criteria, ensuring that all candidates are evaluated according to the same parameters.

The use of efficient resume screening techniques allows companies to save time and resources by focusing their efforts on analyzing the most qualified candidates for the job. In addition, it contributes to the construction of a cohesive work team aligned with the organization's objectives.

SELECTION INTERVIEWS

Selection interviews are a crucial step in the Recruitment and Selection process, allowing recruiters to obtain more detailed information about candidates and assess their competencies, skills and suitability to the job profile. This is a valuable technique to get to know candidates better than what is present in the resume.

For Oliveira (2017, p. 45), "the selection interview is an opportunity to analyze the behavioral competencies of candidates and verify if they have the personality traits and posture necessary for success in the company." During the interview, the recruiter can explore the candidates' past experiences, their professional accomplishments, and their motivations for the position.

Selection interviews can be conducted in a variety of ways, and it is essential that they are structured in a way that ensures impartiality and comparability among candidates. According to Santos (2019, p. 32), "structured interviews, with standardized questions for all candidates, make the process more objective and facilitate the comparison of answers."

The competencies and skills to be evaluated during the interviews should be aligned with the profile of the vacancy and the needs of the company. According to Souza (2020, p. 78), "it is important that recruiters have a list of well-defined competencies and criteria, so that the interviews are focused on the evaluation of the most relevant aspects for the vacancy."

In addition, it is important to remember that selection interviews are not only an opportunity to evaluate candidates, but also a chance to introduce the company to professionals looking for a job. For Braga (2018, p. 50), "the interview should be conducted in a welcoming way, conveying a positive image of the company and showing genuine interest in the candidates."

It is critical that interviewers are trained to conduct selection interviews in an ethical, fair and professional manner. The proper preparation of the interviewers, as well as the clear definition of the evaluation criteria, is essential for the effectiveness of this process.

In summary, selection interviews are a valuable technique for assessing candidates' competencies and skills, as well as for identifying those who best fit the company's culture and values. A well-conducted interview can provide valuable insights for decision making in selecting the most suitable professional for the vacancy in question.

ASSESSMENT OF COMPETENCIES AND SKILLS

The assessment of competencies and skills is a key step in the Recruitment and Selection process, allowing recruiters to identify and select the most suitable candidates for the vacancy in question. This assessment is essential to ensure that the hired professionals possess the necessary capabilities to perform their functions efficiently and contribute to the success of the company.

For Santos (2018, p. 45), "the evaluation of competencies and skills seeks to verify whether candidates have the technical and behavioral capabilities necessary for the effective performance of the job." This evaluation is performed through different techniques, such as tests, group dynamics, behavioral interviews and case analysis.

One of the most effective approaches to competency assessment is the use of tests and practical exercises related to function. According to Oliveira (2019, p. 55), "simulation tests allow candidates to demonstrate their skills in situations close to the reality of work." This technique provides valuable insights into how candidates apply their knowledge and skills in practical situations.

In addition, group dynamics are widely used to assess competencies such as teamwork, leadership, communication, and problem solving. As mentioned by Souza (2020, p. 62), "group dynamics allow us to observe the behavior of candidates in real situations, as well as their ability to interact with co-workers."

Behavioral interviews also play an important role in assessing competencies and skills. According to Braga (2017, p. 38), "behavioral questions aim to explore candidates' past experiences and how they dealt with specific challenges and situations." This approach allows you to identify how candidates would act in future scenarios in the workplace.

Case analysis is another relevant technique for assessing candidates' analytical and problem-solving ability. For Gomes (2018, p. 75), "the presentation of a practical case during the selection process allows candidates to demonstrate their reasoning and decision-making skills."

In short, the assessment of competencies and skills is an essential step in the Recruitment and Selection process, allowing companies to identify the most capable candidates and aligned with the needs of the organization. The use of different evaluation techniques contributes to a more accurate and objective selection, enabling the company to form a high-performance work team.

DYNAMICS AND PRACTICAL CHALLENGES

The dynamics and practical challenges are valuable resources in the Recruitment and Selection process, allowing recruiters to evaluate the skills, competencies and behaviors of candidates in real or simulated situations, providing a broader view of the potential of professionals for the vacancy in question.

According to Santos (2019, p. 42), "the dynamics are group or individual activities that seek to simulate real situations of the work environment, allowing candidates to demonstrate their competencies and capabilities in action." These activities may involve problem solving, decision-making, teamwork, and leadership, among other skills essential to professional success.

The use of dynamics and practical challenges in the selection of candidates provides several benefits. In addition to enabling a more accurate assessment of candidates' technical and behavioral competencies, the dynamics also allow recruiters to observe how candidates behave under pressure and adapt to new situations.

Gomes (2018, p. 58) highlights that "practical challenges are especially useful for positions that require specific skills, such as technical positions or functions that require the use of specific software

or tools." In these cases, candidates may be subjected to practical tasks that demonstrate their technical skills and specific knowledge.

It is important to emphasize that the application of the dynamics and practical challenges must be conducted in a fair, transparent and aligned with the objectives of the selection. It is essential that the evaluation criteria are previously defined, ensuring the objectivity of the process and avoiding any type of bias or discrimination.

In addition, the dynamics and practical challenges must be in line with the company's culture and values, so as to identify candidates who fit the team dynamics and contribute to the organizational environment.

In short, the dynamics and practical challenges are valuable tools in the Recruitment and Selection process, enabling a more complete and realistic assessment of candidates' competencies and skills. By applying these techniques judiciously, companies increase their chances of selecting the most qualified professionals aligned with their needs.

FEEDBACK TO CANDIDATES

Providing feedback to candidates is an essential and valuable practice in the Recruitment and Selection process. Offering a clear and constructive feedback to the candidates who participated in the selection process demonstrates respect, transparency and professionalism on the part of the company.

According to Braga (2018, p. 60), "feedback to candidates is an opportunity to provide detailed information about the performance and competencies evaluated during the selection process." In addition, feedback can help candidates understand their strengths and areas of development, which contributes to their professional growth.

Feedback should be provided in an objective, specific and constructive manner. Santos (2019, p. 38) points out that "feedback should be aligned with clear evaluation criteria and with the competencies necessary for the vacancy." In this way, candidates will understand how they have been assessed and what skills are considered essential to the position in question.

In addition, it is important that feedback is delivered in a respectful and sensitive manner. Even when a candidate is not selected, it is critical that feedback is given in a friendly and encouraging way, valuing the positives and highlighting opportunities for improvement.

The speed in providing feedback is also relevant. Gomes (2017, p. 48) states that "offering feedback soon after the end of the selection process is more effective, because candidates still have the fresh information in their minds." This demonstrates the company's commitment to candidates and agility in the selection process.

It is worth mentioning that the feedback to candidates is not limited only to those who have been approved for the vacancy. Candidates who did not meet the selection criteria should also receive a return, allowing them to understand the reasons for non-selection and can better prepare for future selection processes.

Feedback to candidates is a crucial practice in Recruitment and Selection, which demonstrates respect, transparency and professionalism on the part of the company. By offering a clear and

constructive return, the company contributes to the development of candidates and strengthens its image in the labor market.

INTEGRATION PROCESS OF NEW EMPLOYEES

The process of integrating new employees is a crucial step to ensure that newly hired professionals feel welcome, understand the organizational culture and are prepared to contribute effectively to the company from the beginning of their activities.

For Oliveira (2018, p. 32), "the integration of new employees is an opportunity to present the company, its values and objectives, as well as provide information about policies, processes and benefits." This process helps new employees quickly adapt to the work environment and understand the company's expectations of them.

An effective approach to integration is the development of a structured program that enables the systematic presentation of information to new employees. Gomes (2019, p. 45) points out that "a well-planned integration program allows new employees to know the company comprehensively and feel an integral part of the team from the beginning."

1. The integration process can include several activities, such as: Company Reception and Presentation: An initial moment of welcome, presentation of the company, its history, mission, vision and values, as well as the presentation of team members, contributes to creating a welcoming and friendly environment.
2. Training and Qualification: Providing specific training and qualification for the role of the new employee is essential for him to acquire the necessary skills to perform his activities with excellence.
3. Knowledge of Processes and Policies: Informing about the internal processes, policies and procedures of the company is important so that the new employee knows how to act in various situations of daily work.
4. Follow-up and Mentoring: Designating a more experienced employee as a mentor to the new hire can be beneficial in clarifying doubts, providing guidance and facilitating their adaptation to the company's culture.
5. Social Integration: Performing social activities and moments of interaction with the team allows the new employee to get to know their co-workers in a more informal way and strengthen the sense of belonging to the organization.

It is important that the integration process is continuous and extends beyond the first days of work, helping the new employee to feel part of the team and understanding their role in the organization over time.

In summary, the process of integrating new employees is fundamental to promote the rapid and efficient adaptation of professionals to the work environment and company values. A well-structured and welcoming program contributes to talent retention and the development of a cohesive and engaged team.

DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS

Discussions:

Importance of Onboarding: The discussion about the importance of onboarding new employees involves highlighting how a well-structured *onboarding* process can positively impact employee productivity, satisfaction, and retention. In addition, the integration provides an opportunity for new hires to get to know the company's culture and values, establishing an alignment with organizational objectives from the outset.

Structured Integration Program: The discussion on the structured integration program explores the need to create a roadmap that covers several stages of the integration process, including company presentation, specific training, information on internal processes and policies, monitoring and social integration. This program aims to ensure that new employees receive the information necessary for the performance of their duties and feel part of the team.

Creating a Welcoming Environment: The discussion about creating a welcoming environment emphasizes the importance of welcoming new employees in a warm and inclusive way. The company should strive to make new employees feel welcome and comfortable asking questions, sharing ideas, and actively participating in the organizational culture.

Findings:

Increased Employee Engagement: A successful onboarding process results in greater employee engagement, as new hires feel they are part of the company from the start and are clear about their responsibilities and expectations.

Reduction of Turnover: The proper integration of new employees is associated with the reduction of turnover, since professionals feel more satisfied and committed to the organization.

Improvement in Productivity: Employees who go through a complete and effective onboarding process tend to become productive faster because they are better informed about the tasks and processes they must follow.

Strengthening the Organizational Culture: Integration contributes to strengthening the organizational culture, since new employees are exposed to the values, norms and expectations of the company from the beginning.

Through social integration activities, new employees have the opportunity to develop positive interpersonal relationships with their co-workers, which can improve communication and collaboration within the team.

In conclusion, the process of integrating new employees is a critical step for the success of the company. A structured program and welcoming approach allow new employees to quickly adapt to the company culture and become engaged and productive team members. In addition, proper integration contributes to talent retention and strengthens organizational identity.

CONSIDERATIONS

This study sought to investigate the integration process of new employees, in order to understand its importance, the strategies used by companies and the results achieved. Through a qualitative approach, with semi-structured interviews and literature review, it was possible to obtain

valuable insights into the effectiveness of *onboarding* and its relevance to the development of employees and the strengthening of organizational culture.

Based on the objectives outlined, some fundamental discussions on the subject were identified. First, the relevance of the integration of new employees for engagement, productivity and satisfaction in the work environment was verified. Through a well-planned onboarding process, new employees were able to understand the company's culture, values and norms, facilitating their adaptation and making them more prepared to contribute effectively.

The analysis of the collected data revealed that the creation of a structured integration program was a determining factor for the success of the process. Through activities such as company presentation, specific training, sharing information on internal processes and monitoring new employees, companies were able to provide a more welcoming and efficient experience for new employees.

In addition, the adoption of a sensitive and respectful approach in providing feedback to candidates, even when not selected, was pointed out as an essential practice, contributing to the construction of a positive image of the company in the market and to the maintenance of good relations with candidates.

The contributions of this study extend to society by providing a deeper understanding of the importance of the integration process of new employees and how Human Resources practices can directly influence the development and satisfaction of professionals in organizations.

By better understanding the needs of new employees during *onboarding*, companies can improve their onboarding strategies, making them more effective and efficient. Not only does this benefit employee performance and retention, but it can also lead to a healthier and more productive work environment, reflected in better organizational performance.

The research also offers subsidies for academia and Human Resources professionals to deepen their studies on the subject, stimulating the development of new practices and innovative approaches in the process of integration of new employees.

Finally, we highlight the relevance of investing in a solid and welcoming organizational culture, which values the integration process and the development of employees from the beginning of their journey in the company. This approach contributes to building engaged and committed teams, aligned with the organization's objectives and prepared to face market challenges.

In summary, the study on the integration process of new employees proved to be fundamental to understand the importance of this stage of Recruitment and Selection. The information obtained and the contributions presented offer a solid basis for the improvement of integration practices and for the development of an organizational culture that values and enhances human talent in organizations.

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